

THE ROLE OF THE GULF REGION IN INTERNATIONAL RELATIONS

Abdullayev Mirzobek Bakmamatovich

Tashkent State University of Oriental Studies, 1st year master's degree in
"International Relations and World Politics"

e-mail: mirzaabdullayev17@gmail.com

Abstract: In this article, the role of the Gulf region in international relations and its geopolitical, geoeconomical, and geostrategical importance are covered in detail. Also, the opportunities and shortcomings of the Gulf region are thoughtfully covered.

Keywords: The Ashgabat Agreement, "North-South" international transport corridor (INSTC), Persian Gulf-Black Sea Corridor, "Shia expansion", Shell, Exxon Mobil and British Petroleum (BP).

1. ENTRY AND VALIDITY. Since there is some conflicting difference regarding the status of the Persian Gulf, which is called the Arabian Gulf in some sources, it would be more appropriate for us to apply the concept of the Gulf region to this region. The Gulf region is a continuation of the Indian Ocean, located between Iran and the Arabian Peninsula. Connected to the Gulf of Oman in the east by the Strait of Hormuz, this region includes a large area stretching along the northwestern coastline of the Shatt al-Arab River Delta. The coasts of the following countries are washed by the Persian Sea: Iran, the United Arab Emirates, Saudi Arabia, Qatar, Bahrain, Kuwait, Iraq and Oman, and these countries are called the Persian Gulf countries. Historically and from today's point of view, it is a key point that serves as the main bridge connecting the countries of the Gulf region with the Indian Ocean.

Today, in the foreign policy strategies of most countries, the security of energy resources, the development of energy infrastructure and the formation of the general energy system are recognized as the main geopolitical factors. In particular, as a result of the emergence of new approaches to energy security in the security of the Gulf region, the attitude towards the oil and gas policy, which has a traditional priority in the politics of the countries of the region, is becoming more centralized. The fact that the countries of the region, which are among the largest oil exporters in the world, are located in the Gulf region, can show how important this region is in terms of geopolitics, geoeconomics and geostrategy. If we pay attention to this as an example of numbers, Saudi Arabia, Kuwait, the United Arab Emirates (UAE), and Iraq today have two-thirds of the world's total oil reserves. 63% of the world's oil reserves and 40% of gas reserves

are located in the region. Two countries in the region have 35 percent of the world's oil reserves: 26 percent in Saudi Arabia, 9 percent in Iran.

Also, the Gulf region is one of the most important strategic regions in the world, and one of the reasons for its strategic importance is the presence of the Strait of Hormuz. The crescent-shaped Strait of Hormuz connects the Gulf region with the Sea of Oman and is a point of great economic and strategic importance for major powers among the world's eleven straits.

Another important aspect of the Gulf region is its military and strategic dimension. From a military point of view, the presence of many naval, air and land bases in the Gulf region, where the influence of the US and Great Britain is somewhat higher, as well as the presence of Western warships, especially American ones, in the Gulf region this shows the military and strategic importance of the region. The tanker war that took place in the Iran-Iraq war was one of the factors of the military participation of Western countries, in particular, the United States, in the Gulf region.

Commenting on the place and importance of the Arab world on the world political map, political scientist and orientalist Z. Munavvarov puts forward the following theses:

- Today, it is noteworthy that there are 21 countries that declare themselves as Arab countries, regardless of the existence of certain political, economic, socio-cultural differences, even differences and conflicts between them;

- The community of Arab countries is located in a geographical region where vital communications are centered, connecting the three great continents of the world - Asia, Africa and Europe (through the Mediterranean Sea and Turkey);

- The natural resources on the land of the Arab countries, in particular, the energy source, which is the main support of today's development - oil and gas reserves, ensure the high position of this region in the world economy;

The Middle East is located at the intersection of Asia, Africa and Europe. In addition, in terms of geopolitical importance, it is considered as a border with the Middle East, the Caucasus and Central Asia, and occupies a very important place in geostrategic and geopolitical imperialism, including the hegemony project of major powers. The Middle East region is an important transport corridor of the world. In addition, the location of the Gulf region in the Middle East region and the fact that the main transport corridors pass through the Gulf states show how closely the Gulf region is connected with the Middle East region. For example, we can take the important geostrategic transport corridors that connect Central Asia, Europe, the Caucasus, South Asia and partly Eurasia:

• The Ashgabat Agreement is a multimodal transport agreement between the governments of Kazakhstan, Uzbekistan, Turkmenistan, Iran, India, Pakistan and Oman to create an international transport and transit corridor to facilitate cargo transportation between Central Asia and the Persian Gulf. The agreement entered into force in April 2016. .

• On September 12, 2000, at the second Euro-Asian transport conference, an agreement was signed between Russia, Iran and India on the establishment of the "North-South" international transport corridor (INSTC). The contract on the official opening of the corridor was signed in May 2002. Later, Azerbaijan, Armenia, Belarus, Kazakhstan, Oman, Syria joined the project. Turkey and Ukraine have also applied to join the INSTC.

• Persian Gulf-Black Sea Corridor: Iran, Georgia, Armenia, Azerbaijan, Bulgaria and Greece are in talks to launch a new multimodal corridor. The corridor is expected to be a major hub for rail freight and a multi-modal corridor connecting it to Azerbaijan's Nakhchivan enclave, before traveling to Yerevan and Tbilisi, via a north-south rail link in the northwestern Iranian city of Julfa.

2. METHODS AND LEVEL OF STUDY. The article used the principles of statistical analysis and systematization, as well as methods such as comparative, systematic analysis, and partial swot analysis.

3. RESEARCH AND RESULTS. The fact that the Gulf region is located in the Middle East also shows that it is of great importance in international relations and that it is necessary to take into account the influencing factors in this region. In particular, according to the analysis of the Russian expert L. E. Popova: the complexity of the relations between the countries in the Gulf region is affected by historical, political, religious, social, ethnic, geographical and economic factors and complicates the situation. For example:

1. Struggle for regional leadership among regional countries. A number of countries in the Gulf region are seriously competing for leadership. Claimant religious countries (Saudi Arabia and Iran)

2. The presence of conflict between Shias and Sunnis in the Gulf region;

Based on the above factors, the political realities and frequent changes in the configuration of forces in the Gulf region are causing some difficulties in ensuring peace and stability in the region and predicting the future of the region. Therefore, it is necessary to take into account the following main trends in the provision of geostrategic balance in the region:

In the Gulf region, the influence of the religious factor on the domestic and foreign policies of the states is strong. Forms of appearance:

- struggle between religious and worldly (secular) management;
- the struggle between the religious-ideological competition between the Sunni and Shia currents in Islam, the relationship between Iran and Saudi Arabia;

In particular, there is a struggle between the two streams of Islam, Sunnis and Shiites, that is, a de facto struggle between the Kingdom of Saudi Arabia and Iran and their supporters. After the revolution in Iran in 1979, there was a danger of "Shia expansion" towards the Persian Gulf states. Of course, the fact that Saudi Arabia regularly obstructs this can also show how the countries of the Gulf region are located in opposite environments. In the Gulf region, Shiites make up the majority of the population of three countries: Iran (80 percent), Iraq (60 percent), and Bahrain (about 60 percent), as well as Saudi Arabia and the UAE, which have large Shiite communities. This shows that the Gulf region is divided into two poles in an undefined manner in international relations.

The main role of the oil-producing countries of the Gulf region in the world economy is determined, first of all, by their huge hydrocarbon potential. The economic and socio-political processes taking place in this region have a direct impact on various world problems - economic growth rates, geopolitical situation, relations between civilizations, and others. Since the second half of the 20th century, oil has become the most important raw material for almost all countries in the world, so the largest oil exporting countries began to have a significant impact on the world economy.

The countries of the Gulf region are the largest oil producing and exporting countries in the world. Thus, the share of the region in world oil production is 32 percent, the richest country in hydrocarbon resources, Saudi Arabia, accounts for more than 13 percent of world production. Because of this high level, these countries, which are 6 out of 8 of the OPEC (Organization of the Petroleum Exporting Countries) member countries, can influence the world oil price by reducing or increasing oil production. In addition to national companies, multinational oil concerns such as Shell, Exxon Mobil and British Petroleum (BP) conduct exploration and production activities in the region. In addition, Iran and Qatar are among the top five natural gas producers.

In 2022, its oil flow averaged 21 million barrels per day (b/d), or the equivalent of about 21% of global petroleum liquids consumption. In the first half of 2023, total oil flows through the Strait of Hormuz remained relatively flat compared with 2022 because increased flows of oil products partially offset declines in crude oil and condensate. The Strait of Hormuz, located between Oman and Iran and connecting the Persian Gulf and the Arabian Sea, is the most

important oil transit facility in the world. Next, the Strait of Malacca passes 15.2 million barrels per day. There are 4 ports in the Persian Gulf and the Red Sea, which are among the first hundred ports in the world in terms of cargo turnover: El Jubail (Saudi Arabia, 92nd place), Jeddah (Saudi Arabia, 74th place), Bandar Abbas. (Iran, 51st place), Dubai (UAE, 24th place). These factors explain the most important strategic role of the region for the world economy. Any conflict or political tension in the Middle East can have a significant impact on the global oil market.

Most of the region's oil exports go to Asia and Oceania. Thus, through the Strait of Hormuz alone, 85 percent of oil is sent to Asian markets, where China is the largest oil importer. India, Japan, South Korea and China import more than 5.6 million barrels of oil per day. These countries are the main buyers of Arab oil. For example, 60% of Oman's oil exports go to China, and it also imports much of Iran's oil, which is not delivered to North America at all due to sanctions. In general, the need for hydrocarbon raw materials of Asian countries, where the world economy is developing rapidly, is mainly met by the countries of the Gulf region. They also account for the majority of oil imports in the Middle East.

CONCLUSIONS. In conclusion, it can be said that today the political strategy of many state organizations is the development of energy resources, energy infrastructure, and recognition of the main issues in general energy as the main geopolitical quality. It is no exaggeration to say that this will raise the role and position of countries rich in energy resources in international relations. Therefore, as an example, we can cite the countries of the Blind, and the scope of the new power center is increased more than ever due to its influence on energy resources. The main reason for this is the demand for energy resources of the modern world, on the one hand, and on the other hand, the geostrategic importance of the Gulf outlet connecting the areas of Asia, Europe and Africa, which shows that the development of this area provides security measures to power centers. is happening. opens a big door for influence in world politics. At the moment, countries that have an important enterprise in modern world politics are declaring the Gulf region as their vitally important territory.

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